

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 6.11 Branding Plan and Material

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Table of Contents

- 1. Introduction 4
- 2. CYCLOPES Logo 5
- 3. CYCLOPES Identity Guidelines 6
 - 3.1. CYCLOPES Graphics 6
 - 3.2. CYCLOPES Leaflet 8
 - 3.3. CYCLOPES Roll-up 9
 - 3.4. CYCLOPES Presentation Template 10
 - 3.5. CYCLOPES Deliverable Template 10
 - 3.6. EU-Acknowledgement 11
- 4. CYCLOPES Social Media 12
 - 4.1. Twitter 12
 - 4.2. LinkedIn 14
- 5. CYCLOPES Website 14
 - 5.1. Design & Structure 15
 - 5.2. Security and Maintenance 16
 - 5.3. GDPR compliance 16
- 6. Conclusion 17
 - 6.1. Summary 17
- List of Figures 18
- List of Tables 18

1. Introduction

This document is part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package - WP6 and it outlines the project branding and materials that will follow in order to ensure coherent presentation and well-defined imagery of the project throughout all its activities and interactions with stakeholders. Thus, this document defines the first visual identity of the project that will eventually enhance recognition of CYCLOPES project and its activities across the targeted audiences and beyond.

Varied communication channels will assist widespread distribution for the dissemination of CYCLOPES content, widening the audience and the relevant stakeholders.

The document includes the following sections:

- Section 1: Introduction
- Section 2: CYCLOPES logo
- Section 3: CYCLOPES identity guidelines
- Section 4: CYCLOPES social media
- Section 5: CYCLOPES website
- Section 6: CYCLOPES media for print
- Section 7: Conclusions from this deliverable and future work

2. CYCLOPES Logo

The CYCLOPES logo (Figure 1), was designed at the project proposal stage to represent visually and in text the project name and what the project stands for. The dots located in the logo represent the expanding network but more importantly the cooperation between the various stakeholders. The main colors chosen for the logo (Table 2) are yellow and navy blue. These colors have also set out the main color palette that will be used in all reporting templates.

Figure 1 CYCLOPES project logo

Table 1 Colours in various conversions from Logo

HEX	RGB	HSL	CMYK	COLOR
#05347e	5,52,126	217, 92, 26	96, 59, 0, 51	
#edcd4f	237,205,79	48, 81, 62	0, 14, 67, 7	

The CYCLOPES logo should be included in all presentations and materials that are used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by the partners within the CYCLOPES project.

Moreover the logo should be attached in all deliverables and reports submitted to the EC as well as all partners who have a presence online in the form of websites are recommended to attach the logo of the project to their website and include a link that opens the CYCLOPES project web pages: <https://cyclopes-project.eu>

3. CYCLOPES Identity Guidelines

There are a number of templates and marketing materials produced at proposal stage and later on in the project. Such materials include for instance several project graphical concepts, media materials such as roll-up, leaflet and internet pages, presentation and deliverable templates. These materials, except for the project concepts, will be continuously developed and updated. More on them and their usage guidelines can be found further below in this section.

During May 2021 it was decided that the main background theme of the project will be black with bright fonts (Table 2), either white or blue as seen in the project website: <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. This color will be used only in the website and marketing materials. The reporting and presentation templates will use white background.

Table 2 Main background colour used in the dissemination materials

1

HEX	RGB	HSL	CMYK	COLOR
#231F20	35,31,32	0.96, 0.06, 0.13	0.00, 0.11, 0.09	

It is imperative that the project partners start using the aforementioned materials as soon as they are made available for dissemination efforts, deliverable submissions to the EC portal as well as project presentations and keep track of their updated versions in order to ensure the message is always in line with the current project progress.

3.1. CYCLOPES Graphics

Project graphics have been created at the project proposal stage in order to illustrate different parts of the project, i.e. work methodology, work packages, tasks supporting one another, collaborations with other projects and networks and so on. Moreover they also lay out the first foundation of the project image that is created among the targeted audience. The color palette falls within the two main logo colors with the dominating blue and yellow. As such these

Figure 2 Overall project's methodology

graphics are seen also suitable to be used throughout the project wherever deemed appropriate to represent the project. (Figures 2 - 4)

Figure 3 Overall concept of CYCLOPES project

Figure 4 Practitioners' workshops methodology

3.2. CYCLOPES Leaflet

The CYCLOPES Leaflet is designed in a similar fashion as the roll-up and the website. It is an A5 document that includes a brief description of the project, its objectives, funding, partners as well as a call to action that will be added in order to invite potential network members to join the network (Figure 5).

Figure 5 CYCLOPES leaflet

3.3. CYCLOPES Roll-up

The CYCLOPES Roll-up is one of the main materials designed to catch the attention of potential audiences especially when the audience is able to physically or digitally see them. Roll-ups serve as a first touch point with the project and paint the first impressions. Experience has taught us that they are the most effective when used while representing the project to varied audiences that are in crowd or passers by, but also in keynote speeches, vlogs or video conferences.

As such the Roll-up is designed to be minimalistic, representing the theme of the project via the chosen color palette in line with the website and the logo. Furthermore it describes the project objectives, the funding apparatus, the partners and the contact details to invite further questions/collaboration opportunities (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Project roll-up

3.4. CYCLOPES Presentation Template

CYCLPOES project has created a presentation template for the Microsoft PowerPoint in order to be used in project presentations. The template includes the initial slides with basic information about the project such as the colors, stripes, project logo, content formatting and the EU acknowledgement. These will remain static and unchanged unless a new official version is released. The rest of the content is to be modified and adopted according to the partner's requirements.

This template represents the standardised, and thus, the preferred layout of each presentation. It is recommended that partners prepare presentations related to the CYCLOPES project in accordance with this template (Figure 7).

3.5. CYCLOPES Deliverable Template

With a similar purpose as the presentation template, a deliverable template has also been created for the project it should be used by project partners whenever official deliverables are to be written and submitted to the EC portal.

Figure 7 CYCLOPES presentation template

Figure 8 Deliverable template

The template not only serves as guideline on how the deliverable should be structured, it has already pre-filled formatting and administrative information supporting the writer to quickly start on the content itself (Figure 8 - 9).

Figure 9 Deliverable template

3.6. EU-Acknowledgement

All project dissemination and documentation materials should use the EU-funding acknowledgement in accordance with the grant agreement. This includes the sentence below and the EU-flag logo (Figure 10) .

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669

Figure 10 EU funding acknowledgement

4. CYCLOPES Social Media

As we have seen through experience, social media platforms offer a great opportunity to target desired audiences to keep them updated with project progress. Their simplicity in publishing content and their openness offer an easy way to reach audiences regardless of the device. The WP6 leader and the project coordinator have decided that for our specific project needs, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts would be more favorable as opposed to Facebook, Instagram and other platforms.

4.1. Twitter

A twitter account has been created for the CYCLOPES project called project-cyclopes. (Figure 11). The initial plan was to name the account cyclopes-project, the same as the website, however this at the time was unavailable. Another limiting factor was that the account name had to be comprised of no more than 15 characters. We will be in touch with the social media platforms in order to see if the former account can be released for our use.

To support project activities we will use the (@) mentions as well as (#) hashtags where appropriate, in order for our posts to be easily found by interested parties.

The current hashtags planned are the following:

- #cyclopesnetwork
- #cyclopesproject
- #cybercrime
- #cybersecurity
- #H2020

- #EU

Figure 11 CYCLOPES Twitter account

4.2. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account has also been created and named **project-cyclopes**. (Figure 12) (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-cyclopes/>). With the same vision in mind as the Twitter one, LinkedIn has been recognised as the best platform aimed at reaching professionals which allows posting longer content than Twitter. With that in mind we will use LinkedIn to promote network expansion and keep our followers updated with project news and materials. Here we also faced a similar issue of the name being already taken hence we kept the same name as the Twitter one. Similarly to the Twitter platform, we will be in contact with LinkedIn admins to see if the name can be released for our use.

Figure 12 CYCLOPES LinkedIn Social media account

5. CYCLOPES Website

From M3 onwards, CYCLOPES will have its own dedicated website which will serve as the primary channel to support communication and dissemination of project information and results. The website will maintain the same graphical identity as the other communication tools used within the project.

The website will be accessible from desktop as well as mobile devices on the following address <https://cyclopes-project.eu>. It will host publicly available content produced by the project such as relevant upcoming events, news, public deliverables, project information, network information and so on.

The current version of the website at the time of writing this deliverable is still in development, therefore it is expected that the final version might differ slightly for the one described here.

5.1. Design & Structure

The website is following a simplistic yet modern design, focusing on user needs with its ease of navigation and lightweight structure. There are no planned reactive features that move or adjust while the user navigates the site. This approach will benefit the cross-device usability, making it lightweight even for slow connection speeds (Figure 13).

Figure 13 CYCLOPES website homepage

The current structure might receive slight changes throughout the project as the project matures and more information and/or needs are identified (Figure 14).

Figure 14 CYCLOPES website structure (draft version)

5.2. Security and Maintenance

During the website design and planning phase, the importance of Security was stressed. The React1 library was selected for the website. React is a modern component-based user interface (UI), that is an open source project managed by Facebook and several smaller companies. The library is actively developed and continually upgraded, meaning it a secure option for web developers in addition to providing increased performance and smooth usability.

The backend of the website sits on the common WordPress CMS, which is largely recognised and utilised across the world. Security is paramount for WordPress' reputation and credibility and there are regular updates and security patches released to maximise security.

The team has avoided excessive use of third-party plugins that can sometimes weaken the security structure of a website/application.

Also, the website utilises additional security measures such as reCAPTCHA2, which provides protection without additional interaction from users. "reCAPTCHA2 uses an advanced risk analysis engine and adaptive challenges to keep malicious software from engaging in abusive activities on your website."

The C&D team will regularly review the website traffic and user behaviour to monitor security threats, and will keep the systems patched and upgraded when possible to ensure they are providing adequate protection.

5.3. GDPR compliance

A link to the privacy policy will be provided as a pop-up banner to the users to read before accessing the website. This will inform the user of the data we gather, any tracking performed and the cookie policy. The user will have the choice to continue using the site under the set conditions or navigate away.

An agreement policy will be prepared and the visitors will be informed on the reasons we collect any information and how this information will be used, as in the case with newsletter subscriptions, contact forms and registration to platforms. Visitors will have the right to request to know the data we hold on them and for its destruction upon request. However, some data of offending visitors, performing suspicious actions on the website, may be held for security and forensic purposes.

¹ <https://reactjs.org/>

² <https://www.google.com/recaptcha/about/>

6. Conclusion

6.1. Summary

This deliverable briefly presents CYCLOPES's initial dissemination efforts and supporting strategies. Moreover, it includes details of the branding and identification tools such as logotype, identity guidelines and communication and dissemination channels, which consist of the website and social media platforms. These channels will be operated by the CYCLOPES Communication and Dissemination team, while the content will be provided by all partners.

Due to the tight scheduling and conflicting timetables with some of the partners, few of the dissemination materials were slightly delayed from their initial planned release. Draft versions have been included in this deliverable in order to submit the deliverable on time. Their final versions will be released several days from their planned release and will be included later in the dissemination and communication as well which is scheduled for M6.

List of Figures

Figure 1 CYCLOPES project logo 5
Figure 2 Overall project’s methodology 6
Figure 3 Overall concept of CYCLOPES project 7
Figure 4 Practitioners’ workshops methodology..... 7
Figure 5 CYCLOPES leaflet 8
Figure 6 Project roll-up 9
Figure 7 CYCLOPES presentation template..... 10
Figure 8 Deliverable template 10
Figure 9 Deliverable template 11
Figure 10 EU funding acknowledgement..... 11
Figure 11 CYCLOPES Twitter account..... 13
Figure 12 CYCLOPES LinkedIn Social media account 14
Figure 13 CYCLOPES website homepage 15
Figure 14 CYCLOPES website structure (draft version)..... 15

List of Tables

Table 1 Colours in various conversions from Logo 5
Table 2 Main background colour used in the dissemination materials 6